

UNIVERSITY CLINICAL CENTER TUZLA
TUZLA, BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

<http://www.ukctuzla.ba>

ISSN 0350 – 364X

Acta Medica Saliniana

Special Issue for the 112th annual Days of BHAAAS in Mostar 2021, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Official Medical Journal Of The
University Clinical Center Tuzla
Tuzla, Bosnia and Herzegovina

“Gymnasium Mostar” is gymnasium in Mostar, B&H; Formerly called Gimnazija “Aleksa Šantić” in honor of the eponymous poet, it is nowadays popularly referred to as Stara gimnazija (The Old Gymnasium). The school was ceremoniously opened on 26 October 1893.

June 24-27, 2021, Mostar, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Acta Med Sal 2021; 51- Supplement 1: S1-Sxx

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UNIVERSITY CLINICAL CENTER TUZLA
BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

ACTA MEDICA SALINIANA (Acta Med Sal)

Issued two times a year

ISSN 0350-364X

eISSN 1840-3956

Owned and published by
University Clinical Center Tuzla
Bosnia and Herzegovina
<http://www.ukctuzla.ba>

Acta Medica Saliniana Editorial Office

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Printing office:

Annual subscription rates:

Students 5.00 BAM

Individuals 24.00 BAM

Institutions 48.00 BAM

International 35.00 €

Registration at Federal Ministry of Science of Bosnia and Herzegovina

No. 04-15-5368/04 (14.12.2004.)

The paper is acid-free.

Date of print: November 2021

Circulation: 350

USE OF MOBILE APPLICATIONS FOR MONITORING THE LEVEL OF PHYSICAL ACTIVITY ON THE OCCURRENCE OF POSTURAL IMBALANCES

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Background:

Mobile devices have revolutionized the way people take care of their health thanks to mobile health monitoring applications. According to surveys of mobile device manufacturers, it is claimed that as many as 58% of all smart phone users have downloaded a health-related application. Aim: To determine the impact of the use of mobile applications for monitoring the level of physical activity in order to prevent the occurrence of postural imbalance of students.

Methods:

The study involved 68 students with some form of postural imbalance who filled out a specially designed questionnaire on the use of mobile applications (pedometer, myfitness pal, etc.) to monitor the level of physical activity.

Results:

It was found that all respondents used smart phones. Students rated their health as very good in 58.9%, good

in 20.5% and poor in 20.6% of cases. A difference (53.1% versus 46.9%) was observed, which was statistically significant ($p = 0.003$) in respondents who use one of the mobile applications for monitoring the level of physical activity in self-assessment of health and monitoring the level of physical activity. A statistically significant correlation was observed ($r = 0.87$, $p = 0.004$), which indicates that a more intensive use of mobile applications leads to better self-assessment of health.

Conclusion:

The use of mobile applications for monitoring the level of physical activity leads to an increase in the level of physical activity and a better self-assessment of health, which increases awareness of one's own health and reduces the possibility of postural imbalances.

Key words: mobile application, health self-evaluation, postural disbalance, physical activity

REHABILITATION OF SEVERE SENSORIMOTOR POLYNEUROPATHY IN PATIENT WITH COVID-19 – CASE REPORT

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Aim:

To report the clinical course of sensorimotor polyneuropathy as a peripheral nervous complication in a patient with severe COVID-19, and to discuss possible modalities of physical therapy and rehabilitation.

Case report:

A 69-year-old man was admitted to the COVID-19 department of Infectious Diseases Clinic with clinical and radiological deterioration due to bilateral

COVID-19 pneumonia and consequent respiratory failure. On the 24th day post onset of symptoms, the patient developed a subjective feeling of numbness of the dorsal area of both feet, dominantly right, and experienced difficulties walking and leaning on the same heel. Clinical examination showed significant weakness of the right foot and ankle dorsiflexors, as well as bilateral lower limb sensory impairment, presented as the „stocking pattern“ hypoesthesia. The analysis of the electromyoneurographic findings revealed severe axo-